

Lobeglitazone Sulphate: Unveiling the Therapeutic Potential of a Novel PPAR Agonist in Diabetes Care

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ABSTRACT

In the presence of insulin resistance, the antihyperglycemic medication lobeglitazone enhances both peripheral and hepatic insulin sensitivity. This inhibits hepatic gluconeogenesis and boosts peripheral and splanchnic glucose uptake. Insulin resistance and dysfunctional beta cells are two features of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Only the thiazolidinediones (TZDs) are the primary targets of the oral anti-diabetic medications now on the market. Through the activation of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor, TZDs increase insulin sensitivity. Due to their powerful glycemic effectiveness and low risk of hypoglycaemia, rosiglitazone and pioglitazone have been used extensively for the treatment of T2DM. The usage of these drugs has however, diminished due to safety concerns and adverse effects such as bladder cancer and cardiovascular difficulties. To meet the requirements for an effective and safe thiazolidinedione (TZD), Chong Kun Dang Pharmaceutical Corporation developed the innovative TZD lobeglitazone. With a lower effective dose and positive safety outcomes, lobeglitazone exhibits similar glycemic effectiveness to pioglitazone. In preclinical and clinical investigations, it also exhibited pleiotropic effects. In this article, our objective is to present a comprehensive overview of lobeglitazone, an oral medication used for managing type 2 diabetes mellitus. We will specifically focus on its pharmacological, pharmacokinetic, and therapeutic attributes.”

Keywords: Diabetes mellitus type 2, Lobeglitazone, Thiazolidinediones

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic condition characterized by insulin production, insulin action, or both resulting in hyperglycemia. Chronic hyperglycaemia produced by diabetes is thought to cause long term impairment to multiple organs, including the eyes and kidneys^[1]. Diabetes can result in major complications such as heart failure^[2], diabetic nephropathy^[3], and diabetic foot^[4], may cause serious societal burdens in addition to harming patients^[5].

The primary objective in the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is the effective management of blood glucose levels. T2DM, a chronic and progressive metabolic condition characterized by insulin resistance and β -cell dysfunction^[6], has led to the development of various oral anti-diabetic drugs (OADs) aimed at addressing its complex pathophysiology. Among these OAD classes, thiazolidinedione (TZDs) primarily target insulin resistance^[7].

In the late 1990s, Thiazolidinediones (TZDs) emerged as a class of oral anti-diabetic medications designed to enhance insulin sensitivity by activating the peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor (PPAR)^[8]. The initial TZD, troglitazone, received approval for the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) but was withdrawn from the market in 2000 due to concerns over hepatotoxicity^[9]. Subsequently, other TZDs, rosiglitazone and pioglitazone, gained FDA approval in 1999 and became widely used for T2DM

Due to their potent glycemic effectiveness and minimal risk of hypoglycaemia, these management options exhibited enduring glycemic regulation^[10, 11]. However, owing to safety concerns, including cardiovascular risks^[12] and possible associations with bladder cancer^[13], the utilization of rosiglitazone and pioglitazone has been restricted or substantially decreased since the 2010.

Lobeglitazone, a thiazolidinedione (TZD), is a recent addition to the landscape of diabetes medications. It was developed by Chong Kun Dang Pharmaceutical Corporation in Seoul, Korea.^[14] The TZD medication class has been associated with a decrease in macrovascular risks^[15]. Lobeglitazone, a new peroxisome proliferator activated receptor-

agonist with a TZD moiety, exerts its antihyperglycemic action by directly enhancing pancreatic beta cell survival and function.^[16,17] Lobeglitazone is quickly absorbed into the bloodstream and subsequently eliminated in a monoexponential manner. Only a minimal amount is excreted in the urine.^[18, 19]

Lobeglitazone, a distinctive thiazolidinedione, was specifically designed to meet the need for an effective and safe TZD. The development program for lobeglitazone was initiated by Chong Kun Dang Pharmaceutical Corporation in May 2000, and it received approval for the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) in Korea in July 2013. While further research is needed, lobeglitazone has shown promising efficacy and safety in previous studies. Its potential benefits in managing type 2 diabetes mellitus make it an area of interest for researchers and clinicians alike. In this article, we will delve into the pharmacological, pharmacokinetic, and therapeutic attributes of lobeglitazone.

LOBEGLITAZONE CHARACTERISTICS

The thiazolidinedione medicine class includes lobeglitazone (brand names Duvie and Chong Kun Dang), an anti-diabetic medication. It functions as an insulin sensitizer because it is an agonist for both PPAR α and PPAR γ . By attaching to the PPAR receptors in fat cells, it increases the sensitivity of those cells to insulin^[20]

Lobeglitazone sulfate Duvie TM tablet (0.5 mg), which was initially approved, also functions as a PPAR-agonist and contains a TZD.

Lobeglitazone belongs to the 2, 4 -thiazolidinedione pharmacophore group, and it is linked to this group via an ethoxybenzyl N-methylamino connection. Its chemical name is 5-[4-(2-[6-(4-Methoxyphenoxy)-pyrimidin-4-yl]-methyl-amino-ethoxy)-pyrimidin-4-yl]-methyl-amino-benzyl], with a structural formula of C₂₄H₂₄N₄O₅-thiazolidine-2, 4-dione hydro sulfuric acid.

Fig. 1. Structure of lobeglitazone

To create lobeglitazone, a p-methoxyphenoxy group was added to the 4-th position of the pyrimidine moiety in the rosiglitazone structure^[21]. This modification significantly increased lobeglitazone binding affinity for PPAR. Docking studies have indicated that this affinity is 12 times greater than that of rosiglitazone and pioglitazone^[21]. The p-methoxyphenoxy group enables extended interaction with the hydrophobic pocket, potentially influencing cyclin-dependent kinase 5-mediated phosphorylation of PPAR at Ser245. This alteration can impact the expression of genes such as adiponectin and adipisin, which are associated with insulin sensitivity, without affecting the overall transcriptional activity of PPAR^[22]

CLASSIFICATION ORAL ANTIDIABETIC DRUGS

FIG: 2 CLASSIFICATION OF ORAL ANTIDIABETIC DRUG

CLINICAL PHARMACOLOGY

Mechanism of Action

In fat cells, lobeglitazone binds to and activates PPAR gamma, which then makes the cells more sensitive to insulin. Lobeglitazone has been demonstrated to lower blood sugar levels, lower haemoglobin A1C (HbA1C) levels, and enhance lipid and liver profiles by facilitating the binding of insulin at fat cells [23]. Lobeglitazone is a pure PPAR-alpha agonist as opposed to Pioglitazone, which is a combined PPAR-alpha and PPAR-gamma agonist.

Pharmacokinetics

In rats, lobeglitazone has an approximate 95% absolute bioavailability.^[24] In humans, the mean steady state clearance (CL_{ss}/F) for a dosage range of 1 to 4 mg was 1.13 L/h. The mean half-life was 10.3 hours within the dosing range.^[25] In both rats and humans, the amount of lobeglitazone excreted in urine was very little.^{[24][25]} The medication has a plasma protein binding efficiency of about 99%.^{[24][26]} The blood-to-plasma concentration ratio was on average 0.636. In the medium used for microsomal incubation, the unbound fraction of lobeglitazone was 0.479.^[26]

The tissue-to-plasma concentration ratio of lobeglitazone was 5.59, with the heart, lung, and fat receiving less of the drug overall. In rats, the tissue to plasma concentration ratios for the major tissues ranged from roughly 0.25 to 4.0.^[24]

Lobeglitazone interacts with OATP1B1, OAT3, and MDR1 among the six primary membrane transporters that the US Food and Drug Administration advises.^[24] Lobeglitazone was a substrate of rodent OATP1B2 in vitro.^[27] CYP1A2, 2C9, and 2C19 all had interactions with lobeglitazone.^[24]

In rats, atorvastatin prevented lobeglitazone from reaching the liver.^[28]

A CLINICAL PROFILE OF LOBEGLITAZONE

Glucose regulation in type 2 diabetic mellitus

Monotherapy

A randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, phase II research was used to assess the short-term glycemic effectiveness of lobeglitazone^[29]. For 8 weeks, T2DM patients (n=241) were given lobeglitazone 0.5 mg, 1 mg, or 2 mg, or a placebo (n=55)^[30]. After eight weeks of therapy (the primary endpoint), changes in fasting plasma glucose levels were -20.65 mg/dL (0.5 mg), -23.38 mg/dL (1 mg), -33.69 mg/dL (2 mg), and -1.8 mg/dL (placebo). The minimal effective dose of 0.5 mg once daily was chosen as the standard dose for future analysis because the frequency of Edema increased with greater doses of lobeglitazone.

The glycemic effectiveness of lobeglitazone 0.5 mg (n=115) and placebo (n=58) was then examined over a 24-week period in a phase III research^[31]. Compared to the placebo group, the lobeglitazone group saw mean changes in glycosylated haemoglobin (HbA1c) of -0.44% from baseline to week 24 (the primary endpoint), with a mean difference of -0.6% (P 0.0001). Patients who finished the 24-week study participated in a 28-week open-label extension study^[32] and either kept taking lobeglitazone (n=65) or switched from placebo to lobeglitazone (n=29). The drop in HbA1c observed at week 24 was maintained in those patients who took lobeglitazone for 52 weeks; the mean HbA1c change from baseline to week 52 was -0.50%. After dosing, HbA1c increased in patients who switched from placebo to lobeglitazone at week 25. Similar to that observed in the group who stayed on lobeglitazone for the full 52 weeks, and the mean drop in HbA1c from baseline to week 52 was -0.52%.

COMBINATION THERAPY

A 24-week, randomized, double-blind, non-inferiority study was conducted to evaluate the antihyperglycemic effects of combining lobeglitazone with metformin^[33]. Patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) who were already on a stable dose of metformin (1,000 mg/day) but had inadequate blood sugar control (HbA1c 7% to 10%) were randomly assigned to receive either lobeglitazone 0.5 mg daily (n=128) or pioglitazone 15 mg daily (n=125) as an additional therapy to metformin. After 24 weeks of lobeglitazone add-on therapy, the mean change in HbA1c (the primary endpoint) was 0.74%, which was nearly identical to the change observed in the pioglitazone group (mean difference, 0.01%; 95% CI, -0.16% to 0.18%), demonstrating that lobeglitazone was on par with pioglitazone in terms of its ability to reduce blood sugar levels.

In a separate randomized controlled trial, the addition of sitagliptin (n=126) was found to be non-inferior to lobeglitazone add-on therapy (n=121) in terms of glycemic efficacy (mean change in HbA1c -0.79% vs. -0.86%; difference, 0.08%; 95% CI, -0.14% to 0.30%) over a 24-week period^[34].

To date, there have been no prospective randomized studies comparing the glycemic effectiveness of dual-combination therapy involving lobeglitazone with other oral anti-diabetic drugs (OADs), apart from those comparing it to metformin. In a retrospective analysis, the glycemic efficacy of lobeglitazone was evaluated both as monotherapy and in various combinations.^[35]

This study, conducted in a real-world clinical practice setting, involved 423 patients who used lobeglitazone continuously for more than 180 days (average age 62.7 years, average T2DM duration 8.5 years, baseline HbA1c). The average change in HbA1c after 350 days of lobeglitazone treatment was -0.6%. For lobeglitazone monotherapy, it was -0.34%, for combination therapy with metformin, it was -0.52%, for combination therapy with dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitors, it was -0.63%, and for combination therapy with a sulfonylurea, it was -0.33%. For patients on triple therapy, the mean change in HbA1c was -0.84% for those taking lobeglitazone, metformin, and a DPP-4 inhibitor, -0.88% for those on lobeglitazone, a DPP-4 inhibitor, and a sulfonylurea, and -0.33% for those on lobeglitazone, metformin, and a sulfonylurea. These results suggested that lobeglitazone combined with DPP-4 inhibitors may be more effective at lowering blood sugar levels compared to previous lobeglitazone combination regimens.

Variable	Lobeglitazone mg/day	(0.5)	Pioglitazone (30 mg/day)
Monotherapy, short-term ^[31,37,38]			
Week	24	16	26
Baseline HbA1c, %	7.85	7.50	10.2
Change in HbA1c (placebo subtracted), %	-0.44 (-0.60)	-0.80 (-0.60)	-0.30 (-1.0)
Monotherapy, long-term ^[32,39,40]			
Week	52	52	52
Baseline HbA1c, %	7.79	8.69	8.70
Change in HbA1c, %	-0.50	-1.41a	-1.40a
Add-on to metformin ^[33,41]			
Week	24	24	24
Baseline HbA1c, %	7.93	7.96	8.40
Change in HbA1c, %	-0.74	-0.74b	-0.98

TABLE: 1 Based on prospective randomized controlled studies, lobeglitazone glycemic efficacy in individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus was compared indirectly to that of pioglitazone. Glycated haemoglobin, abbreviated HbA1c.

As the study design allowed for dose escalation up to 45 mg per day, a dose of 15 mg per day of pioglitazone was utilized. It's important to note that unless otherwise specified by superscript letters 'a' or 'b,' all pioglitazone data are derived from studies employing a dose of pioglitazone at 30 mg once daily.

In a recent prospective observational study, the specific impact of first-line triple combination therapy, which included lobeglitazone, was assessed in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) exhibiting HbA1c levels between 9.0% and 12.0% ^[36]. This study employed matching based on body mass index and age to select a comparison group of individuals who received traditional stepwise dual therapy. In comparison to those who received up-titrated treatment with metformin at 1,000 mg/day plus glimepiride at 2 mg/day, patients receiving initial triple therapy comprising metformin at 1,000 mg/day, sitagliptin at 100 mg/day, and lobeglitazone at 0.5 mg/day experienced a significant reduction in HbA1c levels by a mean of 3.28% after 12 months ($P > 0.05$). This trial provided evidence supporting the efficacy and safety of lobeglitazone as part of combination therapy for T2DM, with a particular focus on the success of the initial triple therapy."

Pioglitazone-related comparisons indirectly

As monotherapy, lobeglitazone and pioglitazone have not been directly compared in any randomized studies. Based on pertinent research, Table 3 and Fig. 1 provide an indirect comparison of the glycemic efficacy of lobeglitazone and pioglitazone ^[31, 33, 37, 41]. Lobeglitazone and pioglitazone appeared to have comparable glucose-lowering effectiveness in people with similar baseline glycemic control. Although some trials' findings appeared to indicate that pioglitazone may have a more powerful effect, it should be emphasized that those studies included patients who had higher baseline HbA1cs.

Fig 1. Drawing from previous prospective randomized controlled studies, we conducted an indirect comparison of the glycemic effectiveness of lobeglitazone and pioglitazone in individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus. We explored scenarios involving brief monotherapy, long-term monotherapy, and the addition of these drugs to metformin monotherapy. Our primary focus was on assessing changes in glycosylated haemoglobin (HbA1c) levels

Drug interactions

In studies examining potential drug interactions in healthy male volunteers, there were no significant alterations observed in the pharmacokinetics of either drug when lobeglitazone was coadministered with other antidiabetic agents, such as metformin, glimepiride, dapagliflozin, and sitagliptin [30, 42, 43]. In general, the 90% confidence intervals (CIs) for the geometric mean ratios (combination vs. single drug) for C_{max} and AUC fell within the typical equivalence range of 80% to 120%. There were minor exceptions, including a slightly increased steady-state C_{max} for sitagliptin (ratio, 1.1694; 90% CI, 1.0740 to 1.27320) and a slight decrease in C_{max} for glimepiride (ratio, 0.910547; 90% CI, 0.78246 to 1.05960) when coadministered with lobeglitazone. Nevertheless, these changes were not deemed clinically significant [30, 43]

Similarly, no noteworthy alterations in the pharmacokinetics of either drug occurred when lobeglitazone was combined with amlodipine or warfarin [44, 45]. Nonetheless, co-administration with ketoconazole, a potent CYP3A4 inhibitor, led to approximately a 33% increase in lobeglitazone exposure (geometric mean ratio for AUC_{inf}, 1.33; 90% CI, 1.23 to 1.44) [46].

Medical uses

In individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus, lobeglitazone is used to help control blood glucose levels. Both by itself and in conjunction with metformin are acceptable uses [28]

In 2013, the Ministry of Food and Drug Safety in Korea approved lobeglitazone, and there is a planned continuation of postmarketing surveillance for the drug until 2019 [28][29].

CONCLUSIONS

According to the studies summarized in this review, lobeglitazone emerges as a novel TZD displaying potent efficacy and a favourable safety profile. Lobeglitazone demonstrates glycemic efficacy comparable to pioglitazone but at a lower effective dose, attributed to its higher affinity for PPAR γ . Given that lobeglitazone is primarily metabolized by the liver with minimal renal excretion, it is anticipated that it can be used in patients with renal insufficiency without requiring dose reduction. Additionally, it may carry a lower risk of bladder cancer compared to other TZDs. Clinical trials conducted so far have yielded positive safety results for lobeglitazone. Further clinical and preclinical studies are expected to provide more evidence regarding the beneficial effects of lobeglitazone and elucidate its mechanism of action.

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